

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence-Powered Project-Based Learning Methodology on Developing Computer Application Skills

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Abstract

The current research aimed to identify the impact of artificial intelligence-powered project-based learning methodology on developing computer application skills in the Information Technology subject among tenth-grade students. The research used a descriptive approach and a single-group experimental approach. The research sample consisted of (30) female students from the tenth grade. The research tools and materials included a list of the most important artificial intelligence tools, a list of the most important computer application skills, a guidebook for the artificial intelligence-powered project-based learning methodology, and an observation card to measure the development of the computer application skills aspect. The research results yielded several findings, the most important of which was the significant impact of the artificial intelligence-powered project-based learning methodology on developing computer application skills in the Information Technology subject among the research sample. The research also recommended the need to pay attention to the artificial intelligence-powered project-based learning methodology due to its importance and effectiveness in enriching the educational process.

Keywords: *Project-based learning methodology, artificial intelligence, computer application skills development.*

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Introduction

Twenty-first-century societies are experiencing numerous changes that force their individuals to adopt new behaviors to keep pace with the basic components of life. The emergence of modern inventions, various types of technological means, and artificial intelligence with its various tools and techniques has led to a scientific revolution in various areas of real life. This requires developing the role played by educational institutions in preparing a generation possessing superior skills, capabilities, and abilities that enable them to move forward with life's changes.

The modern technological developments and outstanding technical achievements of the twenty-first century have also highlighted the importance and necessity of focusing on utilizing these technologies to develop students' computer application skills to produce effective students who can keep pace with the demands of the modern era (Omran, 2020, 73).

One of the most important of these technological developments is the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence. Project-based learning is primarily based on the principles of constructivist theory. It also focuses on situational learning and focuses on the student's initial cognitive structure and prior experiences, which have a significant impact on their future learning. It also builds on the process of practicing real-life problems and working to solve them (Schneider, 2005).

Project-based learning is a dynamic approach to modern teaching, where students are exposed to real-life problems, challenges, and difficulties, enabling them to acquire new skills and abilities while learning in active, interactive, collaborative groups. Project-based learning also builds on positive student participation, which supports students' skills in research, investigation, thinking, and innovation, unlike traditional learning situations based on rote learning and memorization (Boss & Krauss, 2007, 12).

The project-based learning methodology also extends to various academic subjects, not just one. Most research has confirmed the feasibility of using this methodology in teaching various subjects at various educational levels. Research has also indicated its preferable use in computer science, given the subject's connection to practical application (Ali, 2009, 11).

The project-based learning methodology can achieve the best and most successful tangible results for students in computer science, as computer science provides an appropriate environment for students to practice various practical exercises. Furthermore, the use of the project-based learning methodology develops many practical computer-related skills (Al-Harbi, 2016, 804).

In light of the expansion of e-learning and the widespread advancements in technology and artificial intelligence, it has become increasingly important to provide students with a variety of technological skills. These skills play a significant role in developing students' computer application skills, fostering effective communication among students, and enabling them to solve various life problems they encounter (Omran, 2020, 72).

Artificial intelligence and its tools are among the most important modern technologies and mechanisms resulting from the scientific and technological revolution the world is currently experiencing. Artificial intelligence tools have emerged through various programs, codes, applications, and smart systems that have significantly impacted the lives of societies and impacted all segments of society. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a new field that emerged from the interaction with technology and its derivatives. AI seeks to understand, analyze, and explain the nature of human intelligence and attempt to simulate and interact with it, in order to create new mechanisms and techniques of smart computers and the ability to study and use them in more systematic and interactive ways. They can also be programmed to perform many tasks that require a great deal of planning, inference, analysis, synthesis, understanding, deduction, memory, innovation, and discovery, all of the features that characterize the human mind, and which fall under the list of intelligent human behavior, as previously it was not possible for an automatic device to have these features (Thalajah & Khawalid, 2012, 7).

Since traditional educational environments, known for their traditional classrooms and teaching methods based on traditional lectures and textbooks, are incapable of accomplishing the higher tasks of higher mental processes, nor can they achieve some ordinary educational objectives, the current era, with its rapid technological progress, cannot cope with these environments. Furthermore, current students require modern methods that are far removed from rote learning, indoctrination, boredom, and repetition in acquiring knowledge. Contemporary students, enabled by artificial intelligence mechanisms and technological advancements, are digital students who can learn at an extremely rapid pace using parallel processors and mechanisms. Artificial intelligence mechanisms and techniques perform these tasks, bridging cognitive, scientific, and communication

gaps, while developing the computer application skills necessary for various students, regardless of their educational background (Dabash, 2022, 13).

Based on the above, the importance of developing students' computer application skills becomes clear. This is to produce students capable of facing life's challenges and obstacles; students capable of research, analysis, implementation, and correct thinking in a functional manner; and students capable of keeping pace with the demands and challenges of the future. Based on what previous research and studies have indicated regarding the importance of a project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence in developing computer application skills, the current research seeks to identify the impact of a project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence on developing computer application skills in the computer science subject among tenth-grade students.

Research Problem

The understanding of the research problem emerged from the following points:

A. Contemporary global trends calling for the necessity of providing students with computer application skills that enable them to coexist properly with the digital age and its mechanisms, and enable them to develop their abilities, skills, and scientific potential.

B. Based on the fact that numerous studies and research have confirmed the importance of the project-based learning methodology in developing students' skills and providing them with special abilities and superior potential, such as the study by Imran (2020), the study by Losif and Lakavos (2009), the study by Ali (2009), the study by Al-Nahhal (2016), and the study by Al-Harbi (2016).

C. Based on the fact that most studies have called for the necessity of utilizing artificial intelligence tools to develop the entire educational process, including objectives, mechanisms, and outcomes, and to utilize them in developing computer application skills and increasing students' knowledge of technological means. Examples of these studies include the study by Dabash (2022), the study by Thalajah and Khawaled (2012), the study by Shaaban (2021), and the study by Darwish and Al-Laithi (2020). D- After reviewing previous studies that emphasized the importance of the project-based learning methodology, studies that called for the need to utilize artificial intelligence tools, and studies that confirmed the weakness of students' computer application skills, the researcher conducted a survey of (20) male and female tenth-grade teachers to determine the extent of students' computer application skills. The results of the survey revealed that 85% of teachers confirmed that students had a weakness in computer application skills. E- To ensure that the research problem was fundamental and important to students' lives, the researcher applied a student needs scale to (30) male and female tenth-grade students. The scale was divided into two parts: one, the cognitive aspect, to determine the extent of students' knowledge related to computer application skills, and the other, the skill aspect, to determine the extent of students' computer application skills. The results of the exploratory study were as follows:

Table 1. The Results of the Exploratory Study

#	field	Number of phrases	Total score	Average student scores n=20
1	Cognitive aspect	20	20	%8.63
2	Skill aspect	30	30	%11.93
The total		50	50	%20.56

The data in the previous table demonstrate a weakness among students in computer application skills. Some students and teachers surveyed in the exploratory study attributed this weakness to the traditional method used by teachers when explaining the educational material in the classroom.

From the above, the research problem is defined as identifying the impact of a project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence on developing computer applications in the Information Technology subject for tenth-grade students.

Research Questions

The research problem is represented by the following main question: What is the impact of a project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence on developing computer application skills?

From this question, the following sub-questions branch out:

1. What is the role of the project-based learning methodology in developing computer application skills among tenth-grade students?
2. What is the role of artificial intelligence in developing computer application skills among tenth-grade students?
3. What are the most important artificial intelligence tools that work to develop computer application skills among tenth-grade students?
4. What are the most important computer application skills that should be developed among tenth-grade students?
5. What is the impact of the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence on developing computer application skills in the subject of information technology among tenth-grade students?

Fourth: Research Objectives

The current research aims to:

1. Identify the role of the project-based learning methodology in developing computer application skills among tenth-grade students.
2. Identify the role of artificial intelligence in developing computer application skills among tenth-grade students.
3. Identify the most important artificial intelligence tools that work to develop computer application skills among tenth-grade students.
4. Identify the most important computer application skills that should be developed among tenth-grade students.
5. Identify the impact of the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence on developing computer application skills in the subject of information technology among tenth-grade students.

Fifth: Research Importance

The importance of the research is determined as follows:

1. Providing a theoretical framework for the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence.
2. Developing a methodology that works to develop computer application skills.

3. Drawing the attention of specialists and educators to the computer application skills that should be developed among tenth-grade students.
4. Assist curriculum developers in general, and IT curriculum developers in particular, with the results of current research and benefit from it.
5. Open the way for researchers to conduct further studies and research on the importance of project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence.
6. Provide an observation card to measure the development of computer application skills, which can be utilized in teaching IT curricula.
7. Assist teachers in identifying new, effective methods, approaches, and methodologies for teaching and learning IT, and learning how to employ them to develop various skills among their students.
8. Provide curriculum developers with a list of the most important artificial intelligence tools used to develop computer applications for tenth-grade students.
9. Raise awareness among parents about the importance of encouraging their children to use artificial intelligence to develop their computer skills.

Research Limits

The current research adhered to the following limits:

- a) The second chapter (Formula Tabs, Data Tabs, References Tabs, Tab View, Updates in Excel, and the Relationship between Word and Excel) was selected from the Information Technology textbook curriculum for tenth-grade students in both the science and literature sections for the 2024/2025 academic year, by the Kurdistan Regional Government - Iraq, the Ministry of Education, and the General Directorate of Curricula and Publications.
- b) Artificial intelligence tools, represented by: (digital systems in schools).
- c) Some computer application skills, represented by: (formula tabs, data tabs, reference tabs, tab display, updates in Excel programs, the relationship between Word and Excel).
- d) The research sample was selected from (30) female students from the science and literature sections in the tenth grade in the Ainkawa area, who study at Al-Nahrain Secondary School affiliated with the Erbil Outskirts Education Directorate.

Research Materials and Tools

1. A list of the most important artificial intelligence tools that work to develop computer applications for tenth-grade students (prepared by the researcher).
2. A list of the most important computer application skills that must be developed for tenth-grade students (prepared by the researcher).
3. A guidebook for the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence (prepared by the researcher).
4. An observation card to measure the development of the skill aspect of computer applications (prepared by the researcher).

Research Hypotheses

To verify and answer the research questions, the following hypothesis was formulated:

There are statistically significant differences at the 0.05 level between the mean scores of students in the experimental group on the observation card measuring the development of the skills aspect of computer applications in the pre- and post-tests, in favor of the post-test.

Research Terms

1- Project-Based Learning Methodology:

The project-based learning methodology is defined as: One of the important teaching methods that places the student at the center and center of the educational process, through conducting educational tasks and educational projects that allow the student to learn independently from the teacher or through learning in small collaborative groups, enabling each student to construct their own learning. This occurs through supporting and developing the learner's existing knowledge and experience and enhancing their skills. (Abdul Jalil et al., 2018, 166)

The researcher defines the project-based learning methodology procedurally as: a modern learning methodology that encourages effective and independent learning. It enables tenth-grade students, during their second semester of Information Technology, to acquire computer application skills, such as formula tabs, data tabs, reference tabs, tab display, updates in Excel programs, and the relationship between Word and Excel. This is achieved through learning in small, planned activity groups that lead to an effective product by creating educational projects in small, collaborative groups.

2- Artificial Intelligence:

Artificial intelligence is defined as: a dynamic computer software package designed and developed to simulate natural human thinking. This is achieved by utilizing intelligent human behaviors, such as the ability to make multiple inferences and the ability to avoid repeating the same mistakes, enabling it to accomplish its goals and tasks with precision, skill, and speed. (Muhammad and Muhammad, 2020)

The researcher defines artificial intelligence procedurally as: a scientific and technical model programmed to solve complex logical, computational, and algorithmic problems in an e-learning environment. This enables tenth-grade students, after studying the second semester of Information Technology, to develop their computer application skills, including (formula tabbing, data tabbing, reference tabbing, tab display, updates in Excel programs, and the relationship between Word and Excel).

3- Project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence

The researcher defines project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence procedurally as: a modern educational approach consisting of a set of steps undertaken by tenth-grade students in collaboration with one another, where communication and interaction between them occurs through artificial intelligence, ensuring the educational process proceeds collaboratively and collectively. This is to develop their computer application skills, including (formula tabbing, data tabbing, reference tabbing, tab display, updates in Excel programs, and the relationship between Word and Excel), through their study of the second semester of Information Technology.

4- Computer Application Skills:

Computer application skills are defined as: a set of skills acquired through a set of pre-prepared and equipped computer programs, granted or sold by specialized and trusted entities, for use in a variety of purposes and tasks, such as educational, engineering, therapeutic, or industrial applications. These programs have a significant impact and effectiveness for the user, whether a student, patient, or worker. (Mohammed, 2011, 25)

The researcher defines computer application skills procedurally as: the behaviors a student acquires and masters through a number of ready-made programs prepared by educational institutions specializing in program development and design. These programs are used by tenth-grade students and trained within the content of the information technology curriculum. Presentation programs include developing skills (formula tabs, data tabs, reference tabs, tab display, updates in Excel programs, and the relationship between Word and Excel) through a project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

The project-based learning methodology is defined as: One of the educational strategies that seeks to engage students in the educational process, drawing on their existing knowledge, skills, and prior experience. This process is supervised by the teacher to ensure the achievement of the desired educational objectives. This is accomplished by presenting previous knowledge, experiences, and acquired skills within a realistic educational framework (Islam, 2016).

It is also defined as: A systematic teaching method based on active learning, which supports students' energies and helps motivate them to plan and reflect on the knowledge they have acquired, applying it to various tasks. It also supports students' ability to think critically and innovatively, and facilitates the use of artificial intelligence and its various tools, due to its ability to motivate students to communicate and interact continuously, and to express their attitudes, beliefs, and ideas in educational situations in a scientific manner (Al-Shammari, 2011).

The importance of the project-based learning methodology lies in supporting and developing the principle of self-learning among students, through the activities, training, and digital resources it provides that work to achieve educational goals. This methodology can be undertaken independently or in the form of collaborative work with other students. It also supports social relationships among students through effective communication and the distribution of tasks and activities among them. It also works to develop certain personal skills, such as dialogue and constructive discussion. It also encourages students to follow a scientific approach in planning, thinking, and innovation (Al-Sayed, 2017).

The project-based learning methodology, supported by artificial intelligence in its form (digital systems in schools), goes through several stages. Al-Sayed (2017) defines these stages as follows:

The first stage: This is the selection stage, in which the student chooses the project that best suits their capabilities, interests, and level. The second stage is the planning stage, in which the student defines the goals they want to achieve, identifies the tasks and activities they want to complete, and determines the time required to complete these tasks.

The third stage is the implementation stage, in which the student transforms their ideas, plans, and drafts into tangible tools and materials that can be implemented on the ground.

The fourth stage is the evaluation stage, which begins with the student starting the project and ends with the completion of the projects. This means that the evaluation process does not stop throughout the program.

The adoption of a project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence (AI), represented by "Digital Systems in Schools," supports the concept of student-centered learning. Students are able to complete and implement projects and tasks individually or collaboratively in small groups. This enables students to exchange knowledge, opinions, and ideas to support the solution of educational problems, making knowledge more comprehensible and stable. This

methodology also supports lifelong learning, given the renewable and changing nature of the methodology (Al-Babli et al., 2021).

Artificial Intelligence

AI is defined as: a component of technological computer science, capable of interacting with and using intelligent systems in various ways. It also features a set of tools that link it to human intelligent behavior (Shaaban, 2021).

AI is also defined as: a dynamic computer program package designed and developed to simulate natural human thinking. This is achieved by utilizing human intelligent behaviors, such as the ability to draw multiple conclusions and the ability to avoid repeating the same mistakes, enabling it to achieve its goals and tasks with precision, skill, and speed (Mohammed and Mohammed, 2020).

It is defined as: a method for producing and innovating autonomous computers or industrial robots that can be used and controlled remotely by computers equipped with specific intelligent programs and applications that mimic distinct human thinking. It is also a scientific system built on manufacturing, engineering, and innovation processes (Darwish & Al-Laithi, 2020).

It can be defined as: the ability of an information system to provide certain interpretations and analyses related to external data with both accuracy and speed, the ability to utilize this external data for other new tasks, and the ability to use this data to achieve previously defined goals and objectives through flexible adaptation processes (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019, 17).

The objectives of educational programs based on the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence lie in their ability to accomplish many tasks and solve complex problems associated with the educational process. These programs also serve as a quick solution to the problem of weak teacher training capacity and a remedy for the crisis of insufficient teacher numbers for the number of students.

AI-powered educational programs also have several objectives, as outlined by Ismail (2017):

1. These programs are a model for applying AI technology tools and mechanisms in the educational process.
2. They aim to support and develop students' skills in using computer applications during the learning process, enabling them to function as effective and efficient teachers.
3. They support computer applications and educational programs, which are supported and equipped with AI mechanisms and fields.
4. They simulate the role of the teacher in the classroom, including explanation, follow-up, and evaluation.
5. They support individualized learning processes, taking into account individual differences among students, and the ability to provide quality education to diverse students.
6. They support interaction and communication processes between students and the educational application or program provided to them, where communication is conducted in a clear and understandable language, and continuous feedback is provided throughout the program.

There are many types and tools of artificial intelligence (AI) used by learners and teachers to complete educational tasks and achieve various educational goals. Examples include chatbots, digital systems in schools, grading and assessment, smart education systems, personalized learning, distance learning, virtual reality and augmented reality technology, virtual mediators, the Math Thinker app, the Brainly website, which allows learners to ask homework questions and the website provides automatic answers, the Mika website, and the Netex Learning website (Al-Balawi, 2021).

From the above, the researcher finds that various fields, with all their dimensions, have been affected and benefited from AI applications and tools. One of the most beneficial fields is education, which supports the educational process with its various goals and objectives, at various stages and subjects, and in various fields and dimensions. AI plays a significant role in supporting students' skills, emotions, and culture, and providing them with an exciting educational experience. The researcher also identified the AI tools used for the current research in the tool "Digital Systems in Schools." 3- Computer Application Skills:

Computers are the core for building and designing specialized applications and programs. These applications and programs, which have become widespread in the fields of education and learning, play an important role in student learning, supporting their abilities and potential, and developing their computer and educational skills. They also represent effective teaching methods that simplify students' various curricula.

Computer applications are defined as programs developed by software companies or institutions that are used by individuals in an easy and organized manner, following instructions. These applications are based on graphics, designs, videos, and codes, depending on the intended purpose and the nature of the computer user and their work (Hargrave & Andre, 2010, 14).

It is also defined as: a set of programs that appear as windows or command lines, available on the user's tablet or computer. The user can download them from various sources, such as websites or CDs. The classifications and objectives of these programs vary depending on the needs and goals of the users, and on the goals of the company developing these programs. For example, there are office applications, internet applications, therapeutic software applications, gaming and entertainment applications, or specialized applications for educational and pedagogical programs, provided that these applications are compatible with the computer used. These programs can be free or paid (Al-Far, 2012, 32).

Computer application skills are also defined as a set of experiences, activities, behaviors, and practical educational tasks that enable the student to use computer programs easily and conveniently for specific educational goals (Al-Qamish & Al-Jawada, 2012, 214).

The general importance of computer applications is multifaceted, such as their development of logical thinking skills and their efforts to understand the interrelationships between the various variables offered by the applications. They also support direct interaction and communication between the student and the application used through continuous feedback. They are also a powerful motivator and incentive that helps and motivates students. Furthermore, they enable students to maximize their use of educational materials and acquire knowledge and information, as applications can display videos, images, audio, and experiments in their realistic form. They can also control the speed of displaying phenomena or pause the display. The major importance of these applications lies in saving time and effort in performing complex tasks such as mathematical operations and difficult equations. They can also achieve high levels of understanding, interpretation, and analysis, as they rely on the development of higher skills such as thinking, innovation, and criticism through understanding and comprehending relationships, codes, and symbols (Al-Maraghi et al., 2013, 35).

Based on the above, the findings of previous studies, and a review of the information technology textbook prescribed for tenth-grade students, the researcher identified the most important computer application skills that should be developed among tenth-grade students. These six basic skills were identified: (formula tabulation, data tabulation, reference tabulation, tab display, updates in Excel programs, and the relationship between Word and Excel).

Second: Previous studies that addressed project-based learning methodology, artificial intelligence, and the development of computer application skills.

Studies that Focused on Project-Based Learning Methodology

Imran's study (2020) aimed to develop some website design skills among middle school students by applying a project-based learning strategy supported by some Web 2.0 tools in teaching the computer curriculum. The study was based on the experimental approach, and the study sample consisted of 50 male and female students from the second year of middle school, who were divided equally into two groups: experimental and control. The study tools also included a list of website design skills, a website, a teacher's guide, a user's guide, an activity booklet, an observation card, and a final product evaluation card. The study results showed that using a project-based learning strategy supported by Web 2.0 tools helped develop the skills of second year middle school students in designing some websites. The most important recommendations of the research are modern educational strategies and investing them in developing various skills among students, and focusing on developing website design skills among students. The study also recommended the need to benefit from the project-based learning strategy. Al-Yamahi's study (2023) aimed to identify the effectiveness of using artificial intelligence and project-based learning in serving environmental sustainability. The study used a quasi-experimental, single-group approach. The study sample consisted of (85) female third-cycle students. The study tool was a project-based learning strategy. The study results showed statistically significant differences between the study sample members in the project-based learning strategy and in the use of artificial intelligence in the pre- and post-tests, in favor of the post-test.

Muhammad's study (2021) aimed to identify the impact of collaborative project-based learning supported by Google Education applications in teaching environmental education on developing achievement and some mental habits. The study relied on the experimental approach. The study sample consisted of (50) male and female graduate students. The study tools included an achievement test and a Habits of Mind scale. The study results revealed the effectiveness of collaborative project-based learning based on Google Education applications in teaching environmental education, developing achievement and some mental habits among the sample members.

2- Studies that focused on artificial intelligence

Raad Al-Tlouhi's study (2023) aimed to identify the impact of artificial intelligence platforms on e-learning environments during the teaching of Arabic language. The study sample included (30) fifth-grade primary school students, who were divided into two experimental and control groups. The study relied on a quasi-experimental approach and a descriptive-analytical approach. The study tools consisted of an achievement test. The study concluded that the use of artificial intelligence platforms in e-learning environments is important. The study also recommended the use of artificial intelligence techniques and tools to achieve educational objectives. The study of Seven (2022) aimed to develop electronic accounting skills by designing an educational platform based on artificial intelligence to develop electronic accounting skills for business education students. The study sample consisted of 60 students from the second year of commercial secondary school, and they were divided into two experimental groups. The study relied on the experimental approach. The study tools were represented by an achievement test to measure the cognitive aspect related to electronic accounting skills, and an observation card to measure the performance aspect of electronic accounting skills. The results of the study revealed differences between the first and second experimental groups in the post-measurement on both the cognitive achievement test and the performance observation card in favor of the first experimental group that studied using the expert systems application.

Dabash's study (2022) aimed to examine the effectiveness of an artificial intelligence-based e-learning environment in developing English reading skills. The study sample included (60) sixth-grade female students, divided into an experimental group and a control group. The study was based on a quasi-experimental approach, and the study tools were determined by a reading skills

scale. The study results demonstrated the effectiveness and importance of teaching using an artificial intelligence-based e-learning environment in developing oral reading skills in English. The study also recommended the use of artificial intelligence environments in the educational process.

Al-Mutairi's study (2022) aimed to identify the effect of an artificial intelligence-based e-learning environment on developing e-learning skills. The study sample included (60) female students from the College of Education at Umm Al-Qura University, who were divided into an experimental group and a control group. The study adopted a quasi-experimental approach. The study tools included a cognitive selection to measure the cognitive aspect and an observation card to measure the performance aspect. The study resulted in the development of e-learning skills among sample members through an artificial intelligence-based e-learning environment.

Studies that Focused on Computer Application Skills

Abu Naji et al.'s study (2024) aimed to identify the impact of designing a mobile learning environment according to the ARSC model on developing some computer skills. The study relied on an experimental approach. The study sample consisted of 60 primary school students in Kuwait, who were divided into an experimental group and a control group. The study tools included an achievement test for some computer skills and an observation card for some computer performance skills. The results indicated the impact of the mobile learning environment according to the ARSC model on developing some computer skills among sample members. The study of Al-Tahtah (2023) aimed to identify the impact of computer applications (MS Project) on developing the skills of the IT project management team in Saudi Arabia. The study was based on the descriptive analytical approach, and the study sample consisted of (124) specialists. The study tools were a questionnaire. The results of the study revealed a statistically significant effect, with a positive correlation between computer applications and developing the skills of the IT project management team in Saudi Arabia.

The study of Al-Masry and Ismail (2022) aimed to identify the impact of employing role patterns (mixed - leader - specific) in virtual communities of practice according to learning analyses on both the development of computer application use skills and the depth of learning for female undergraduate students. The study relied on the descriptive analytical approach and the experimental approach. The study sample consisted of (60) female undergraduate students, who were divided into three experimental groups. The study tools were an achievement test, an observation card, and a deep learning scale. The results of the study revealed an increase in the level of academic achievement, computer application use skills, and the depth of learning for female students as a result of employing role patterns (mixed - Leader - Specific).

Asiri's study (2020) aimed to identify the reality of the use of computer applications in school administration at the intermediate level. The study used a descriptive-analytical approach. The study sample consisted of (21) principals and vice principals from intermediate schools in Barq Governorate. The study tools consisted of a questionnaire. The results of the study revealed that the degree of school principals' and vice principals' practice of computer applications was "high," while the degree of contribution of current computer applications to school administrative work was "high."

After reviewing previous studies that included research variables, namely project-based learning methodology, artificial intelligence, and computer application development, it can be said that they agreed on the importance of developing students' computer application skills. Most studies also agreed on the weakness of their computer application skills, which calls for attention to the need to develop these skills to achieve educational goals. Most studies also agreed on the importance of project-based learning methodology and artificial intelligence and their role in developing students' skills, abilities, and potential. In fulfillment of the recommendations of previous studies, the

importance of the current research emerges in identifying the impact of project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence on developing application skills. Computer science.

Research Methodology and Procedures

The current research used the descriptive approach when addressing the theoretical framework of the research and reviewing previous research and studies, as well as when constructing the research materials and tools, and during the discussion and interpretation of the results. The current research also used the experimental approach when applying the research tools to the female students, relying on a quasi-experimental design using pre- and post-tests for a single experimental group, as this approach is appropriate for the nature of the current research.

Population and Sample

The research population was selected from tenth-grade female students in the Ainkawa area who study at Al-Nahrain Secondary School, affiliated with the Erbil Outskirts Education Directorate. Their number reached (211) students from both the science and literature departments, with (174) students in the science department and (37) students in the literature department. The research sample consisted of (30) students who were randomly selected. Third: Research Tools:

1. A list of the most important artificial intelligence tools that help develop computer applications for tenth-grade students. This list was prepared by the researcher's review of books and academic sources, by reviewing the objectives of teaching information technology, by examining the academic content assigned to tenth-grade students in information technology, and by obtaining the opinions of information technology specialists. Based on the above, the artificial intelligence tool was identified as "Digital Systems in Schools."
2. A list of the most important computer application skills that should be developed among tenth-grade students. This list was prepared by the researcher's review of previous studies and academic journals, through an exploratory study conducted by the researcher, by reviewing the objectives of teaching information technology, by studying the academic content assigned to tenth-grade students, and by consulting the specialist professors. Based on the above, a list of the most important computer application skills that should be developed among tenth-grade students was identified, namely: formula tabs, data tabs, reference tabs, tab display, updates in Excel programs, and the relationship between Word and Excel.
3. A guidebook for the AI-powered project-based learning methodology. This booklet was prepared to facilitate the study of the selected chapter of the IT curriculum for the tenth grade and to guide the teaching process. The booklet includes a general introduction to the AI-powered project-based learning methodology and its importance as a modern teaching methodology. It also includes the teaching objectives for the selected second semester, the various teaching methods and approaches that should be used during the teaching process, as well as the educational tools used. It also includes a timeline for teaching the second semester. It then includes some guidelines and instructions for teachers and students, as well as activities for each computer application skill, and finally, the final assessment. 4- An observation card to measure the development of the skill aspect of computer applications. It consisted of (6) main skills, in order to measure the skill performance of the research sample in computer application skills, and to identify the extent of development of these skills among students. The card included the following skills: The first skill is formula tabulation, represented by (10) phrases. The second skill is data tabulation, represented by (10) phrases. The third skill is reference tabulation, represented by (10) phrases. The fourth skill is tab display, represented by (10) phrases. The fifth skill is updates in Excel programs, represented

by (10) phrases. The sixth skill is the relationship between Word and Excel, represented by (10) phrases. The researcher presented the card to (20) experts with experience in information technology. The experts' opinions resulted in a very high percentage of agreement on the card's phrases and skills. Accordingly, the number of card phrases reached (60) phrases, divided into (6) main skills.

The observation card phrases were formulated in the form of skills, and the observer was responsible for determining the student's level of proficiency in performing the skill, using a three-point rating scale (proficient, somewhat proficient, and not proficient). The student's score was calculated based on the total score they received. Two marks were awarded if they were able to perform the skill, one mark if they were relatively proficient, and no marks were awarded if they were unable to perform the skill. The validity of the observation card was calculated using the validity of the judges, as previously explained, and through discriminant validity, which was calculated by calculating the significance of the differences between the highest and lowest quartiles using the Mann-Whitney test to calculate the differences between ranks. The reliability of the observation card was calculated using Cronbach's alpha equation, which is used to illustrate the overall reliability of the card. The reliability coefficient of the observation card was 0.892, indicating the stability of the observation card due to its high percentage. The reliability of the card was also measured using the observer reliability method. The researcher gave the card to another colleague, and the correlation coefficient was calculated. The result was high, indicating the stability of the observation card. The following table shows the final form of the observation card:

Table 2. The Final Form of the Observation Card

#	Skill	Number of phrases indicating mastery of the skill
1	Formulas tab	(10)
2	Data tab	(10)
3	References tab	(10)
4	Tube width	(10)
5	Updates in Excel programs	(10)
6	The relationship between Word and Excel	(10)
The Total		(60)

Research Experiment

The procedures for implementing the experimental research process included the following:

1. Content analysis of the tenth-grade information technology curriculum.
2. Preparing research materials and tools, including a list of the most important artificial intelligence tools that help develop computer applications for tenth-grade students, a list of the most important computer application skills that should be developed by tenth-grade students, a guidebook for the AI-powered project-based learning methodology, and an observation card to measure the development of computer application skills, all prepared by the researcher.
3. Presenting the research materials and tools to experts with experience in information technology to make the necessary adjustments based on their suggestions and recommendations.
4. Obtaining administrative approvals from specialists to implement the research experiment.
5. Conducting a pilot experiment on (20) tenth-grade female students to measure the reliability of the observation card.
6. Pre-application of the research tools (the observation card) to the experimental group.

7. Teaching the experimental group using the AI-powered project-based learning methodology.
- 8- Post-application of the research tools (the observation card) to the experimental group.
- 9- Analysis of the results using SPSS.

Results and Discussion

The research hypothesis states: There are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the average scores of the experimental group students on the observation card measuring the development of the skill aspect of computer applications in the pre- and post-tests, in favor of the post-test. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher compared the average scores of the experimental group students in the pre- and post-tests, based on the observation card. The researcher used the paired-samples t-test to detect the significance of the differences between the averages (using SPSS v21). The following table illustrates these results:

**Table 3. The Means, Standard Deviations, and T-values for the Experimental Group Students' Scores in the Pre- and Post-Measurements of the Observation Card
N = 30 and 29 Degrees of Freedom**

Card skills	Application	Average	standard deviation	T value	degree of freedom
Formulas tab	before	5,70	0,74	26,49	29
	After	11,53	1,07		
Data tab	before	5,86	0,77	25,46	29
	After	11,76	1,16		
References tab	before	4,50	0,51	23,54	29
	After	8,36	0,72		
View tab	before	4,86	0,77	19,37	29
	After	8,80	0,81		
Updates in Excel programs	before	1,56	0,50	29,00	29
	After	6,40	0,72		
Difference between Word and Excel	before	5,83	0,74	29,84	29
	After	12,46	0,93		
Total score	before	28.31	4.03	57,64	29
	After	59.31	5.41		

Note: * The tabular t-value at 29 degrees of freedom and a significance level of 0.05 = 2.04.

The previous table shows the following:

- Comparing the average scores of the experimental group students on the pre- and post-tests of the observation card, it was noted that the post-test averages were higher than the pre-test averages. The researcher attributed this to the project-based learning methodology supported by artificial intelligence for the experimental group.
- The t-test values were statistically significant at a significance level of (0.05) between the average scores of the experimental group on the pre- and post-tests on the observation card and its various skills. Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted, i.e., there are statistically significant differences at a level of (0.05) between the average scores of the experimental group students on the observation card measuring the development of the skill aspect of computer applications in the pre- and post-tests, in favor of the post-test.

The following graph shows an increase in the average scores of the experimental group on the post-test compared to the averages of the same group on the pre-test on the observation card among tenth-grade students.

Figure 1. The Graphical Representation of the Average Scores of the Experimental Group Students on the Pre- and Post-Tests of the Observation Card

Conclusion

The project-based learning methodology, supported by artificial intelligence, plays an effective role in developing tenth-grade students' computer application skills. This is due to its ability to simplify the scientific material and present it in an attractive and simple format, providing students with an exciting learning experience. It also takes into account individual differences among students, and is important in helping students accomplish difficult tasks and solve complex educational problems. This methodology also helps center learning around the student and supports direct interaction and communication between students. This result is consistent with the results of studies by Al-Tahtah (2023), Al-Masry and Ismail (2022), Dabash (2022), Shaaban (2021), Darwish and Al-Laithi (2020), Al-Nahhal (2016), Al-Harbi (2016), Thalajah and Khawaled (2012), and Ali (2009). Sixth: Research

Recommendations

1. Incorporate artificial intelligence tools into the tenth-grade IT curriculum, given its importance in enriching students' reality and enabling them to embody and simulate it.
2. Employ a project-based learning methodology when teaching other educational subjects.
3. Hold training courses for IT teachers to educate them on the mechanisms for effectively employing artificial intelligence within the educational process.
4. Design training and guidance programs to increase students' awareness and develop their various skills.

5. Focus on supporting and developing students' computer application skills.
6. Focus on promoting the use of artificial intelligence tools among students at various educational levels, especially the early stages.
7. The need for educational institutions to adopt artificial intelligence mechanisms and integrate them into the educational process.
8. Train teachers to produce and design computer applications.

Research Proposals

1. Designing an educational methodology based on artificial intelligence tools to develop various programming languages.
2. The effectiveness of an educational program supported by artificial intelligence tools in developing innovative thinking skills and web (0.2) skills.
3. The impact of a project-based learning strategy on developing augmented reality skills.
4. An evaluative study of the information technology curriculum in light of educational program design skills.
5. The effectiveness of a project-based learning environment in developing virtual journey design.

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